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Object-Oriented Paradigm as a Method for Formalizing Character Properties in Fictional Universes (on the Example of the Character Representation of Nekhlyudov in Leo Tolstoy's Novel “Resurrection”)

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Abstract. The article explores the possibility of applying the object-oriented paradigm (a term from computer science) to formalize various implementations of characters in fictional universes. Examples are provided based on the implementations of the character of Nekhlyudov from Tolstoy's novel “Resurrection”. Possible applications of the discussed approach are examined for analyzing the relationships between different implementations of the same character, as well as for generating new characters based on the individual preferences of the reader (viewer, user).

Keywords: fictional universe, character formalization, object-oriented paradigm, adaptation, novel “Resurrection”, cinematographic adaptation.

Note on terminology: The Russian term “obraz” (образ) denotes a specifically Russian literary-critical concept that integrates image, character, and representation into a unified analytical framework. As no single English word captures this holistic meaning, the compound term “image/character” is used throughout this text to preserve this complexity.

Introduction

Computer methods are being introduced everywhere, including in the humanities (*Digital Humanities*). Existing work in digital philology focuses mainly on computational linguistics, statistical methods for working with text corpora, and the digitization of sources, and less frequently on the representation of

knowledge in the form of semantic networks (Gomonova, 2020; Berti, 2019). At the same time, the potential for using computer methods is obviously broader: despite claims that programming in its modern form is gradually becoming a thing of the past (Welsh, 2023), computer science has accumulated many approaches for the formal representation of interrelated objects. Such objects can include literary characters. This article focuses on the possibility of applying an object-oriented paradigm to formalize (literary) characters from “fictional universes” that have many “incarnations” and, as a result, exhibit a phenomenon known as “property inheritance”. It should be noted that this article does not claim to provide a comprehensive analysis of Tolstoy's character Nekhlyudov, but demonstrates the possibilities of applying a specific programming methodology to analyze a corpus of all possible implementations of a (literary) character.

Character. Network. Universe

A character (in the broadest sense) “exists” in various implementations¹: from representation in the author's mind, through the image/character imprinted in the text and then reflected in the reader's mind, and further - in some cases - to theatrical, screen, or even game incarnations². The totality of all such embodiments constitutes a *corpus of all possible implementations of the image/character*, the size of which is practically unlimited due to the countless number of readers (viewers, users). At the same time, a specific character becomes a connecting link, uniting works of different types and genres into a kind of “network”. Such a “network” or “interconnected network of movies, television, comic book, gaming, and internet content”³ (Havard et al., 2019, p. 10) in media discourse is increasingly referred to as a “fictional universe” or simply “universe”. The term “universe” in the context under discussion was first introduced, apparently, by D. Markstein⁴, a noted historian of comics and animation. Today, fictional

¹ Hereinafter, implementation refers to *realization, embodiment*. This term is used in computer science to denote the successive realization of a single entity.

² For example, the character of *Stalker* created by the Strugatsky brothers: from the novel “Roadside Picnic” to the series of computer games S.T.A.L.K.E.R.

³ Let us assume that theatrical productions existing in the media space in the form of record (video versions) or direct live (streams) can also be added to the list.

⁴ This refers to a text by Donald Markstein in the fanzine (1970), which was published by the CAPA-alpha amateur press association, which brought together comic book enthusiasts. The online encyclopedia D. Markstein's Toonopedia has preserved a trace of the text (<https://www.toonopedia.com/universe.htm>), which begins with the phrase: *Tracing out “universes” of comic book characters is fun. This is done by constructing a web of crossovers, starting from a basic character, and seeing how many other characters can be shown conclusively to exist in the same world with him.* The statement regarding the authorship of the term may be justified if one takes into account Markstein's role as a “collector” and researcher of characters, plots, and intertextual intersections from various comics and cartoons.

universes as systems are increasingly becoming the subject of research. However, there are not many works devoted specifically to the characters of universes. This may be partly explained by the broader challenges of character studies: according to the editors of *Characters in Fictional Worlds*, the field suffers from “the gaps between the disciplines” [...] and the fact that “once they are subject to closer scrutiny, characters prove to be highly complex objects in a number of ways” (Eder et al., 2010, p. 3).

It can be assumed that the complexity of a character is related not only to dramatic aspects, for example, but also to the fact that image/character has a different nature (media text/mental representation in the mind), is individual, and is subject to the influence of many factors. Let us consider, as an example, the image/character of Nekhlyudov from Leo Tolstoy's novel *Resurrection*, which gave rise to one of the first “universes”⁵. The image/character of Nekhlyudov is interesting in that the author describes his appearance very sparingly (literally a few words in the third chapter of the first part of the novel), and the reader can only guess what a character like Nekhlyudov might have looked like or been like.

As is well known, there was a real “prototype” for Nekhlyudov, about whom Tolstoy was told by A. F. Koni. Thus, in Koni's mind, the first implementation of the image/character in question “existed” (if we do not take into account the reality of the “prototype”). It can be assumed that Tolstoy, as a listener, formed his own conception (mental image) of the hero of Koni's (oral) story, which influenced the author's synthetic image of Nekhlyudov, which was gradually “born” in Tolstoy's mind as a writer and then embodied in the text of the novel. In turn, in the mind of each reader of the novel *Resurrection*, their own Nekhlyudov is “painted” – an image/character formed under the influence of both the text (for example, from the description of Nekhlyudov's appearance, from the sequence of his actions and reactions to events), and the reader's personal conceptions about what a Russian nobleman (as a kind of archetype) of that era might be like, what Tolstoy's literary hero might be like, etc.⁶ The illustrators of numerous editions of *Resurrection* had their own conceptions (mental images). The screenwriters, directors, cinematographers, makeup artists, and actors of numerous film adaptations of *Resurrection*

⁵ The novel “*Resurrection*” became the basis for theatrical and opera productions, more than 30 screen adaptations and films “based on”, most of which were made outside Russia: from the silent short film “*En Opstandelse*” by Danish director Viggo Larsen (1907) to the Italian “*Resurrezione*” by director Tonino De Bernardi (2019).

⁶ These conceptions extend down to the most fundamental level: the reader's basic understanding of what a human being looks like.

also had their own internal representations of Nekhlyudov's image/character, which, in turn, influenced the corresponding screen incarnations.

In his multifaceted study of “trans-textual characters” in fictional universes, Brian Richardson, drawing on Roland Harweg's criteria, notes that “information from the later works will *add to our knowledge of the character*” (Richardson, 2010, p. 539. Emphasis added. - G.S.). It can be clarified that this “supplementation” is a certain *inheritance* of the character's properties, and we are dealing with a kind of “network” in which each subsequent implementation of the image/character “inherits” the properties of the previous one, while being influenced by numerous “personal” representations (prejudices, stereotypes) of the reader or viewer. The final image/character (whether it is a mental image in the reader's mind or an image on the screen) has certain cumulative properties that only partially “inherit” the properties of its literary “ancestor” in their original form.

To formalize such a network – to enable, for example, the tracing of relationships among image/character implementations, personal conceptions, and other factors influencing the image/character – one may employ either a graphical representation in the form of a schematic diagram or an object-oriented approach involving the declaration of data in a high-level programming language. The second method may be more productive, as its application is accompanied by a process of digitization, and the result is computerized and can be used in computer-oriented applications⁷.

OOP and the image/character of Nekhlyudov

The object-oriented paradigm (or object-oriented programming; hereinafter OOP) is a methodology known in computer science for representing data in the form of classes and objects, based on three basic principles: inheritance (inheritance of the functionality of a parent class or parent object), encapsulation (combining data and program code, isolating the class's “own” data from external use), and polymorphism (the ability of a function to receive data of different types as arguments). It is widely recognized that OOP is useful for representing hierarchical dependencies and entities from a variety of

⁷ For example, in the production of computer games based on a particular character: in games, as in 3D modeling, a character is described in the corresponding programming language precisely as an object with a set of properties. See, for example, Maksimenkova and Veselko, 2022.

subject areas. At the same time, there are two approaches to the class-object pair (Gunter, Mitchell, 1994): the first, implemented in most modern programming languages (*class-based* languages), considers a class as a template for instantiating objects (at the same time, a class, acting as an abstraction, as a kind of model, can be an heir to another class or classes⁸); the second approach, on which *delegation-based* languages are based, allows one object to be created by deriving it from another object, thereby simulating inheritance.

To represent an image/character in such a system, as a *corpus of all possible implementations of the image/character* in its subset – in a “fictional universe”, the second (*delegation-based*) approach is interesting⁹. In this case, we leave the concept of class outside the brackets, and by the concept of object we mean both the image/character itself (literary, mental, on screen) and various personal stereotypes of the reader (viewer). Thus, we unify the *image/character* and *personal stereotypes*, which allows us to describe the *influence* of one on the other as a kind of *inheritance* of properties from one object to another. For example, the reader's perception of the image/character of Nekhlyudov is an *object* that “*inherits*” the properties¹⁰ of at least two other *objects*: the image/character described in the novel and the reader's stereotypical (personal) perception of the image/character of a 19th-century Russian nobleman. In object-oriented programming language, the latter thesis can be written as follows (in general terms):

```
Object Mental image of a participant in real events witnessed by A. F. Koni in Koni's mind {  
    . . .  
};  
  
Object Hero of A. F. Koni's oral story  
    inherits from object Mental image of a participant in real events witnessed by A. F. Koni in Koni's mind {  
    . . .  
};  
  
Object Mental image of the hero of A. F. Koni's oral story in Tolstoy's mind  
    inherits from object Hero of A. F. Koni's oral story {
```

⁸ If a class inherits from more than one class, we speak of “multiple inheritance”.

⁹ The delegation-based approach is used here for the theoretical representation of image implementations – for preliminary analysis. For practical computer experimentation, the author of the article used a class-based approach and a high-level Java programming language.

¹⁰ In this context, it imitates inheritance - it is formed at the expense of other objects, using their properties.

```

    . . .
};

Object Nekhlyudov as a mental image in the mind of Tolstoy as the author of the novel
inherits from object Mental image of the hero of A. F. Koni's oral story in
Tolstoy's mind {
    . . .
};

Object Nekhlyudov as a literary image/character described in Tolstoy's text
inherits from object Nekhlyudov as a mental image in the mind of Tolstoy as the
author of the novel {
    . . .
};

Object Stereotype of a person's appearance in reader X {
    . . .
};

Object Stereotype of a Russian nobleman in reader X {
    . . .
};

Object Reader X's image/character of Nekhlyudov
inherits from object Stereotype of a person's appearance in reader X,
inherits from object Stereotype of a Russian nobleman in reader X,
inherits from object Nekhlyudov as a literary image/character described in
Tolstoy's text {
    . . .
};

```

The sequence of declarations presented above represents only the “upper” layer of abstraction, reflecting the chain of inheritance (*influence*), but does not contain details – specific information about particular properties. For a more detailed formalization at this stage, it is proposed to go for some *simplification* in order to see how the approach under consideration works for a specific array of properties describing the character's *appearance*, leaving aside more general and complex arrays related to evaluative judgments and the reader's (viewer's) emotional attitude toward the character.

OOP and Nekhlyudov's appearance

Tolstoy describes Nekhlyudov's appearance only briefly (the English translation is taken from Tolstoy, Leo. Resurrection. Translated by Louise Maude, introduction by Richard F. Gustafson, Oxford University Press, 2009):

...he put down his smooth, white legs, stepped into his slippers, threw his silk dressinggown over his broad shoulders. ... he washed his hands with perfumed soap, cleaning his long nails with particular care, washed his face and stout neck at the marble wash-stand, and went into a third room where his shower-bath stood ready. Having refreshed his plump, white, muscular body and dried it with a rough bath-sheet, he put on his fine undergarments and his boots, and sat down before the glass to brush his black beard and his curly hair, which had begun to get thin above the forehead.

Formalizing the character's appearance using OOP, we can write the following:

```
Object Nekhlyudov as a literary image/character described in Tolstoy's text
  inherits from object Nekhlyudov as a mental image in the mind of Tolstoy as the
  author of the novel {

    Legs: "smooth, white"
    Shoulders: "broad"
    Nails: "long"
    Neck: "stout"
    Body: "plump", "white", "muscular"
    Beard: "black"
    Hair: "curly", "thinned at the front"

  };
```

It is evident that the available information about his appearance is insufficient: from the text, we do not know, for example, the color of Nekhlyudov's eyes and "curly" hair, the shape of his face, the size of his hands, his height, etc. Therefore, the reader is forced to mentally supplement the image/character of Nekhlyudov based on their own ideas (stereotypes) about what a person looks like and what a nobleman (of the second half) of the 19th century might look like.

Thus, the number of parameters (or fields) in the corresponding object¹¹ is much greater, and they are “filled in” with meanings that are inherited from one's own stereotypes:

```
Object Reader X's image/character of Nekhlyudov
  inherits from object Stereotype of a person's appearance in reader X,
  inherits from object Stereotype of a Russian nobleman in reader X, inherits from
  object Nekhlyudov as a literary image/character described in Tolstoy's text {

    Height: [inherited value]
    Face shape: [inherited value]
    Eye color: [inherited value]
    Arms: [inherited value]
    Legs: "smooth, white"
    Shoulders: "broad"
    Nails: "long"
    Neck: "stout"
    Body: "plump", "white", "muscular"
    Beard: "black"
    Hair: "curly", "thinned at the front"
    Hair color: [inherited value]

  };
```

In a real object declaration, each parameter (in this case, appearance) must have its own “type”, which is a *set* (collection) of precisely defined values-primitives. Let's introduce, for example, the type “EyeColor” and define it as follows:

```
Type "EyeColor" = {Blue, Gray, Green, Yellow, Brown, Black}
```

Thus, for example, the value “EyeColor.Blue” is a *primitive* that is individual for each reader (viewer, user). Obviously, each primitive is associated with a certain experience and formed stereotypes. But how is the value in the descendant object replaced (substituted) by a specific primitive? This question is especially relevant in the case of multiple inheritance: for example, an individual 1) first read a novel; in which 2) he saw an illustration; and then 3) watched the film adaptation. What color eyes will this

¹¹ Strictly speaking, a separate class (interface) can be distinguished, which is a model of a person in the most general sense and already contains the corresponding fields, which are “filled” during the next iteration of inheritance.

“summarized” Nekhlyudov now have in the individual's mind? How does the *preferred choice* of a new *value* work? The mechanism of such a choice is strictly individual. Let's call this mechanism the *individual substitution function*. Such a function can only be determined experimentally, by constructing the most complete “network” of objects (images/characters and stereotypes) for a specific individual (reader, viewer, user).

Conclusions

This article applied OOP principles to formalize Nekhlyudov's appearance within the “universe” of the novel and its adaptations. The proposed framework distinguishes between properties that are textually specified, those inherited from cultural stereotypes, and those introduced by specific adaptations – thereby clarifying how readers and viewers perceive character continuity or its disruption. A natural next step would be to extend this formalization to psychological traits and narrative function.

References

- Berti, M., ed., 2019. Digital Classical Philology. Ancient Greek and Latin in the Digital Revolution. Berlin/Boston: Walter de Gruyter GmbH.
- Eder, J., Jannidis, F. and Schneider, R., 2010. Characters in Fictional Worlds. An Introduction. In: Eder, J., Jannidis, F. and Schneider, R., eds. Characters in fictional worlds: understanding imaginary beings in literature, film, and other media. Berlin/New York: Walter de Gruyter, pp. 3-64.
- Gomonova, I. and Serikova, I., 2020. Computer Philology: A Practical Guide. Gomel: F. Skorina Gomel State University.
- Gunter, C. and Mitchell, J., eds., 1994. Theoretical Aspects of Object-Oriented Programming: Types, Semantics, and Language Design. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.
- Havard, C., Fuller, R., Ryan, T. and Grieve, F., 2019. Using the Marvel Cinematic Universe to Build a Defined Research Line. Transformative Works & Cultures, 30, p. 10. Available at: <https://journal.transformativeworks.org/index.php/twc/article/view/1837/2195> [Accessed 25 December 2023].
- Maksimenkova, O. and Veselko, N., 2022. Programming in Unreal Engine 5 for Beginner Game Developers. Basics of Blueprint Visual Language. Moscow: Eksmo.

Richardson, B., 2010. Transtextual Characters. In: Eder, J., Jannidis, F. and Schneider, R., eds. Characters in fictional worlds: understanding imaginary beings in literature, film, and other media. Berlin/New York: Walter de Gruyter, pp. 527–541.

Tolstoy, L.N., 1996. Resurrection. In: Collected Works in 8 volumes, Vol. 6. Moscow: Leksika. Available at: <https://ilibrary.ru/text/1462/index.html> [Accessed 25 December 2023].

Welsh, M., 2023. The End of Programming. *Communications of the ACM*, 66(1), pp. 34–35.